

Newsletter 1 / 2022

To subscribe to/unsubscribe from this newsletter, please visit:

<https://lists.dkrz.de/mailman/listinfo/esiwace-external>

You find further details on ESIWACE at <https://www.esiwace.eu>.

All newsletters are also available at www.esiwace.eu/newsletter.

Deliverables and milestone documents referred to in the newsletters can be downloaded from Zenodo:
(<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>).

Contents

Save the date	1
Spread the word	2
New coupler version OASIS3-MCT_5.0 is released!	2
Machine Learning Workshop at ECMWF	2
Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in	2
News & updates	3
SC'21 Best Visualization Award for "Putting the Ocean into the Center: A coupled ICON Atmosphere/Ocean Simulation in Spilhaus Projection"	3
Advanced C++ course	3
Redesign and update of the ESIWACE website	5
Recently published ESIWACE2 Deliverables and Milestones	5
Snapshots	6
Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications	8

Save the date

The next **Short Private Online Course (SPOC) on Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT will** most probably take place from **March 20 to April 1st 2022**. Stay tuned, all news will be posted on the OASIS3-MCT training page:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings/training-on-oasis3-mct>

Spread the word

New coupler version OASIS3-MCT_5.0 is released!

The latest version of OASIS3-MCT comes with a number of novelties, which we have listed in our [news item on the tool](#). To obtain the tool, please visit the [OASIS coupler download page](#) provided by CERFACS. Having been funded by both IS-ENES3 and ESIWACE2, the release of OASIS3-MCT_5.0 is an official project deliverable of IS-ENES3 available via the [IS-ENES3 website](#).

Machine Learning Workshop at ECMWF

ECMWF will host a virtual workshop for machine learning from 29 March to 1 April 2022. The workshop will discuss machine learning applications for numerical weather predictions and climate services and will focus on four topics:

- Machine learning for emulation of model components
- Machine learning for forecasts from now-casting to seasonal
- Machine learning for feature detection and user applications
- Machine learning tools and high-performance computing

The registration is free and everyone is welcome to join.

<https://events.ecmwf.int/event/294/>

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [PASC22](#), Basel (CH) / hybrid, 27-29 June, 2022
- [ISC22](#), Hamburg (DE), 29 May - 2 June, 2022
- [EGU22](#), Vienna (AT) / hybrid, 23-27 May, 2022
- [SC21](#), St. Louis, MO, USA, 14-19 November, 2021
- [Training on HPDA for climate data with the Ophidia framework](#), online, 11 November, 2021
- [Advanced C++ workshop](#), online, 11-13 October, 2021

News & updates

SC'21 Best Visualization Award for “Putting the Ocean into the Center: A coupled ICON Atmosphere/Ocean Simulation in Spilhaus Projection”

A team of the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ), the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), Stockholm University, and the Intel Corporation has received the Supercomputing SC'21 Best Scientific Visualization & Data Analytics Showcase Award for their visualisation “Putting the Ocean into the Center: A coupled ICON Atmosphere/Ocean Simulation in Spilhaus Projection”, which was supported by ESIWACE2.

With the award, the Supercomputing Conference 2021 (SC'21) acknowledges the year's most impressive videos in high-performance computing. The 2021 winning video takes us on a journey through the months of May, June and July of a year-long coupled global storm-resolving ocean-atmosphere simulation performed with the Earth system model ICON-ESM.

Unlike for most visualisations of global climate datasets, the team selected the unique view of a Spilhaus projection for their SC'21 video. Showing the world's oceans as one interconnected body of water, the Spilhaus projection puts the ocean into the center, without cutouts or clipping planes and with only minor distortions, allowing the viewer to fully focus on the 3D atmospheric and ocean data and their interaction over time.

The visualisation was created by Niklas Röber of DKRZ, who also presented the showcase at the conference.

Read our [full news article](#) for more details on the conference contribution, simulation data and visualisation techniques employed. To simply watch the winning video, visit our [ESiWACE YouTube channel](#).

Advanced C++ course

In spite of the ongoing Covid pandemic, ETHZ/CSCS moved ahead with its Advanced C++ course (Oct. 11-13, 2021), albeit in a virtual format. The course assumed basic C++ programming knowledge and treated a wide range of topics and use cases that are relevant in the context of high-performance computing:

- Values and Object Initialisation
- Name Resolution
- Templates
- Move Semantics
- Constexpr / Consteval / Constinit
- Lambdas and functions

- STL
- Ranges
- Resource Management
- Concept-based design

These topics varied considerably in complexity and abstraction. Use cases on selected C++ applications and libraries – such as <https://github.com/eth-cscs/DLA-Future> and <https://github.com/kokkos> – were presented towards the end of the course, as was a hands-on session. While the course dealt with a wide range of topics, the unifying goal of the course was to convince the participants of the efficacy of C++ for high-performance computing. Indeed, some advanced features were intentionally left, e.g., inheritance and polymorphism, because they are not key to high performance.

The course was targeted to the general public, but space for 12 ESIWACE2 stakeholders was set aside (11 ultimately participated). Of the 27 participants who filled out the non-obligatory survey on demographics, 20 were male, 4 female and 3 chose not to respond. Many came from computer science or computational mathematics backgrounds, but a large number came from specific scientific disciplines such as crystallography, weather/climate, medicine, economics and molecular dynamics.

Why C++?

- Supported by hardware
- Integrated in established IDEs
- Many available compilers
- Huge online community
- Scales with application complexity
 - Control investment by isolating components
 - Allows API design and implementation
 - Thanks to overhead free abstractions

| 10

There was a wide scope in their backgrounds: the highest level of education achieved was a Bachelors (4), Masters (9), PhD (12), while two had post-doctoral degrees. There was also a wide scope in their career stage, with 13 in their initial career (first 5 years), 9 in their mid-career (5-15 years) and 5 in their later career.

The feedback was generally very positive, with 85% saying that the course either exceeded, met or nearly met their expectations, 90% saying the pace was ‘just right’, and with most giving good or excellent grades for the expertise and preparation of the instructors. However, a number of valid points were brought up by participants, for example:

Image source (comic): <https://xkcd.com>

- The format might have been better suited for an in-person course, changes should be made in the online format, such as shortening the days and/or adding more exercises.
- Several people complained about the lack of hands-on training for the specific topics (as opposed to having a long training towards the end), e.g., “I would also prefer to have some time to exercise with the material that was just explained,” and “Some hands-on sessions were greatly needed!”
- Part of the course was more tailored towards people who are already regularly writing code in C++ and already have quite a good knowledge of C++, rather than only having basic C++ knowledge.

ETHZ/CSCS will take this constructive criticism to heart and will hopefully repeat the course in the next years in person, rather than remotely.

Redesign and update of the ESIWACE website

Over the last few months we have redesigned, restructured and updated the [ESiWACE project website](#) with the goal of introducing ESIWACE2, its relevance and project results in a visually more appealing, informative way with improved usability on both desktop and mobile devices.

We invite you to explore our refurbished website and to discover what is new! The section [The Project](#) is the information hub illustrating how ESIWACE accelerates the development of a new generation of high resolution weather and climate models on upcoming generations of (pre-)exascale supercomputers - from project objectives via models to the bigger picture of the European HPC Landscape and resulting publications and [success stories](#).

In the section [About us](#) we focus on partner institutes and the human dimension of the project: Who are we, which institutes do we work for, which expertises do we bring to the table, what drives us and how do we collaborate within ESIWACE? Meet some of our staff members in the [People](#) section!

To learn about special software packages supported within ESIWACE, public HPC services offered and our training programmes, we refer you to the [Services](#) section. In that section you will also find information on the DYAMOND Initiative.

We are continuing to add new content to <https://www.esiwace.eu> – stay tuned!

Recently published ESIWACE2 Deliverables and Milestones

In December 2021 we released four public project deliverables and two milestones:

D1.1 Simulations of global high-resolution climate and weather models in production mode

Work package 1 of ESIWACE2 aims at developing and running coupled weather and climate model simulations at highest possible resolution with a throughput rate of at least one simulated year per day (1 SYPD), producing full model output. Deliverable D1.1 gives an overview of the main components and algorithms that are used by the

different models currently considered, outlining challenges for the use of pre-exascale machines for weather and climate simulations at very high resolution. It also addresses the topics of scalability and efforts in coupling infrastructure and model in- and output (I/O). [Read the deliverable here.](#)

D5.1 Report on the ESDM runtime extensions for parallel in-flight analytics

This deliverable documents the final release of *Earth-System Data Middleware* (ESDM) runtime extensions for *post-processing, analytics and visualisation* (PAV), the ESDM-PAV runtime. It covers its design, the strategies employed for parallel execution of PAV applications, the approach followed for efficient in-flight analytics on top of the ESDM for improved I/O towards heterogeneous storage back-ends and the related software implemented, as well as providing usage examples. [Read the deliverable here.](#)

D6.1 Report on the summer school and its Material

This report describes the organisation and outcome of the two ESIWACE summer schools in 2020 and 2021, which were held as a week-long virtual event in August 2020 and 2021, respectively. With sessions including about 34 hours of lectures and 18 hours of hands-on and lab practicals, the summer schools aimed at training young researchers and software engineers in methods, tools, and theoretical knowledge to make effective use of HPC environments for climate and weather research, and to generate insights. D6.1 focuses particularly on the training sessions offered and contains ample references to the training material. [Read the deliverable here.](#)

D6.4 Training material made available under a permissive CC-by license

Deliverable D6.4 presents the Open Educational Resources (OER) material created in the context of the trainings on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools for weather and climate modelling delivered via ESIWACE2 work package 6. The training topics covered by the OER material include I/O, DSL, C++, code coupling, data analytics and containerisation. [Read the deliverable here.](#)

To access the OER material for a specific ESIWACE training, visit the [ESIWACE training page](#).

Milestones released:

MS2 - [Production-mode simulation with NEMO, ICON-ESM, ECMWF, EC-Earth, IPSL model](#)

MS9 - [Workflow Extensions](#)

Snapshots

BSC

After the delivery of the Very High Resolution (VHR) configuration of the EC-Earth4 model, BSC is continuing the work to improve the performance and the refinement of the whole workflow in Mare Nostrum 4.

In December 2021, research engineer Xavier Yepes made a two weeks visit to the Alfred Wegener Institute to work on the improvement of the XIOS deployment in the OpenIFS-FESOM2 model. In collaboration with Yann Streffing, they analysed and solved different I/O bottlenecks related to the XIOS server. A contribution for the EGU2022 is being prepared based on the results of this visit.

CERFACS

CERFACS has been actively working on the new version of the OASIS coupler, OASIS3-MCT_5.0, that was released in December! More information in the news item on the tool. CERFACS also produced the final version of the deliverable D6.4 about the OER material based on ESIWACE2 trainings.

CMCC

The development activities on the ESDM-PAV software continued, aiming to improve the integration with HPC infrastructures and to simplify the setup procedure. A new version of the related software packages has thus been released. CMCC led deliverable D5.1 “Report on the ESDM runtime extensions for parallel in-flight analytics” published in December 2021, which describes and documents the developed ESDM-PAV software and the support for in-flight analytics, as well as the preliminary integration with PAV tools and frameworks. CMCC also contributed to the OER material published within the scope of the project, by designing a High Performance Data Analytics course that was uploaded to the OER Commons website.

DKRZ

With a number of project deliverables and milestones due by the end of last year, we at the project office took care of their final review, submission and publication, where applicable.

As part of the project work packages WP1, WP2 and WP5 we took part in writing the deliverables and milestones D1.1, MS2, D5.1 and the confidential deliverable D2.5. For this purpose, final work on a coupled ICON high resolution (10km spatial resolution) production mode simulation had been done and scalability runs were performed.

Work on the redesigned ESIWACE website has been ongoing. More ESIWACE colleagues have volunteered to appear in the new “People” section of the website, and we have published two new success stories on efficiently learning how to use the OASIS coupler and on the development of EC-Earth4.

For the next interim review, we are coordinating, partly writing and supporting our partners in filling the interim report.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

With the new year, CSCS has started working on the M48 deliverable for finalised containerisations of given models. So far the ICON and COSMO teams have agreed to finalise their container work for the deliverable. We will contact the other teams that took their models to the 2019 container hackathon to enquire about the current status.

NLeSC

Gijs van den Oord (NLeSC) presented the work on the ESIWACE2 Service 1 project on RTE+RRTMGP at the AGU Fall meeting in December 2021.

NLeSC and Atos will be working on four new projects that have been granted as part of the last year of ESIWACE2 Service 1. In these projects we will collaborate with model developing communities to port weather and climate models to new architectures and prepare the software for the new generation of supercomputers.

SMHI

SMHI is currently finalising work on the EC-Earth 4.0 release, which is based on the same model version developed and used in work package 1. Thus, results achieved for EC-Earth in this ESIWACE work package will be made available to the community of the EC-Earth consortium.

In another activity, EC-Earth 4 is being ported to new machines with AMD EPYC-based nodes (Atos BullSequana XH2000, HPE Cray EX). This is one of the prevalent architectures of EuroHPC pre-exascale systems, such as LUMI, and therefore an intermediate step towards the utilisation of such machines.

Furthermore, SMHI is currently developing a new tool to approach the time-consuming computation of remapping weights needed to couple ESM components with the OASIS coupler. The latest version, OASIS3-MCT 5.0, is being used to develop a Python-based prototype software that allows for the flexible and efficient creation of weight files for a wider range of computational grids. Even though the EC-Earth 4 VHR configuration (see BSC contribution above) does not depend on the development, the tool might help future configurations to work more efficiently.

UKRI/STFC

STFC contributed to deliverables D2.3 (on DSL interoperability) and D2.5 (Concurrent components). The work on DSL interoperability involved improving PSyclone so that it was able to take a Fortran tracer advection benchmark and translate it into a form (SIR) that the dawn DSL could take as input. Dawn was then able to output optimised CUDA code that validated with the original Fortran benchmark. The work on concurrent components involved analysing the potential of LFRic to make use of concurrent components within the model. Development has continued with using PSyclone to add OpenACC directives to unmodified NEMO source code so that the model will run on a single GPU and the resultant performance continues to increase. We are also running NEMO on multiple GPUs and have encountered performance issues, particularly with the use of GPU direct and managed memory, but the performance here is also improving. In collaboration with the ExCALIBUR Marine Systems project we are also looking at 1) OpenMP offload directives to allow support for GPUs other than NVIDIA, 2) the possibility of using explicit memory transfers, rather than using managed memory, 3) integrating PSyclone into the NEMO build and test suites, 4) using PSyclone to add OpenMP multi-core CPU directives for ECMWF and 5) the possibility of using PSyclone for other marine models, namely nemovar, medusa and wavewatch3.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

M. Klöwer, M. Razinger, J.J. Dominguez, P.D. Dueben, and T.N. Palmer: Compressing atmospheric data into its real information content. Nat Comput Sci 1, 713–724, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-021-00156-2>, 2021

X. Yepes-Arbós, G. van den Oord, M.C. Acosta, and G. D. Carver: Evaluation and optimisation of the I/O scalability for the next generation of Earth system models: IFS CY43R3 and XIOS 2.0 integration as a case study, Geosci. Model Dev., 15, 379–394, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-379-2022>, 2022

The project ESIWACE2 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823988.